

Impact of Condition of Service on Job Performance in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Educational zone, Kano State

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Abstract

The study examined the 'Impact of condition of service on Job Performance in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Educational zone, Kano state.' The specific objective of the study was to examine the impact of remuneration, promotion and staff development on job performance in the post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. The study employed the use of descriptive survey, while the sample of the study was 322 staff derived from the total population of 2,066 staff which is in compatibility with K.C. Morgan table of sample size determination. A random sampling technique was employed in selection of the sample size. A validated researcher designed Questionnaire with 30 items was used to collect the data for the study. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Of mean and standard deviation were used in answering the three (3) research questions. The findings revealed that Remuneration, Promotion and Staff Development affect teachers job performance, to a high extent in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Zonal Education Directorate, Kano State. Based on the findings, the study recommended that the government at all levels should provide Special Teachers Salary Scale, Effective Promotion and Regular Staff Development Programmes.

Keyword: Condition of Service, Job Performance, Remuneration, Promotion and staff Development.

Introduction:

Post Basic Education Schools are parts of the major educational institutions that are required by both 'Individuals and Nations' for educational growth and development. In the schools right there, the Teachers are the most needed Staff as they are in possession of the required professionalism, skills and competencies needed in effective teaching and learning activities. Hence, improvement in the quality of learning, depend to a great extent on the level of their job performance. Selemani-meke (2013) opined that poor condition of service and poor allowances received by the teachers have contributed to their lack of motivation to effectively implement their job satisfactorily at all levels. Thus, (Musa,2015) postulated that, teachers' absenteeism, job dissatisfaction, perceived neglect and excessive grievances have been identified as the most pressing and complex problems confronting the nation's teaching profession. Therefore, teachers supposed to be carefully trained, maintained and supported to enable them successfully deliver the required quality of education to the citizenry. As, the aspiration of any country to transform into educationally developed nation may only become a reality if there are competent and committed teachers who take on the responsibility of impacting the appropriate and needed attitude, skills and knowledge to its human resource (Adegbemile, 2012). This was supported by Eduese (1996) cited in Ige (2014) that teachers are the Pillars on which the architecture of the educational system rest on. According to Musa (2015), prompt payment of salaries not only assist people to attain their basic needs, but also instrumental in satisfying their higher-level need. In a nutshell, teachers' welfare is very low to guarantee efficient service delivery and attainment of the overall objectives of the education. It has been observed that the question of remuneration has much influence on staff motivation, job satisfaction, commitment, performance and productivity (Udeozor, 2004).

Similarly, promotion is believed to be one of the motivating factors amongst staff. According to Musa (2015) it is a positive way of rewarding people for their efforts and services. Sheafter et al. (2018) stated that promotion is pivotal for organizational personnel as it helps enhance individual employee performance. Similarly, Koo et al. (2020), argued that if employees perceive that there has been a dearth of promotion opportunities, they might be dissatisfied with their current jobs. But, if an employee receives a timely promotion to the next seniority post, then such employee will become more motivated and satisfied with the job role (Lup, 2018). Therefore conclusively, Promotion is an essential part of employees' jobs career life as it will affect their attachment and engagement level at the workplace (Kostea, 2011). On the same vein, staff development has been recognized as an essential factor of motivating employees to put in their best in their respective places of work. To Khalid (2007) staff development is concern with the provision of learning, development and training opportunities for employees in an organization in order to improve their organizational performance. The teachers like any other employees

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equally need these trainings and all other opportunities that comes along with promotion. Thus, Aloma (2012) viewed staff development as a process designed to improve job understanding, promote job performance and establish future goals for career growth of workers like the teachers. It is therefore very clear that condition of service, particularly the lower-level needs such as remuneration, promotion and staff development play an essential role in motivating employees to be at their best at work. The extent to which any organization meet up with the needs of its staff, determine the level of their motivation and commitment as well as job performance (Enyi, 2004). Thus, management of human resources through the establishment and maintenance of good condition of service is of paramount importance for all organizations. Hence, nowadays many teachers run away from the educational sector to other sectors that seem to have a better condition of service. The poor pay of academics was confined by the report of the study group on Brain Drain in Nigerian Universities (1982-1993) carried out by the World Bank Project Implementation Unit of the National University Commission. According to Afolabi (2013), due to the poor condition of service and inadequate motivation for the teachers, their performance have fallen. And that many of them have decided to seek for better fortune elsewhere. Based on the above exposition, the study intends to examine the Impact of condition of Service on Staff Job Performance in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Educational zone, Kano State.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study was to examine the Impact of Condition of Service on Job Performance in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Educational zone, Kano. While, the specific objectives of the study are:

1. To examine the extent teachers' remuneration, affects their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano State.
2. To examine the extent teachers' promotion, affects their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano State.
3. To examine the extent staff development, affects teachers job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. To what extent does teachers' remuneration, affects their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state?
2. To what extent does teachers' promotion, affects their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state?
3. To what extent does staff development, affects teachers job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state?

Methodology

Descriptive Survey research design was used in the study. The population of the study comprised all 2066 staff from 79 post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone N.Z.E.D (2021). Sample size of 322 staff was drawn from the study population. Random sampling technique was employed in the selection of the sample size. A self-designed questionnaire with 30 items was used for data collection. The questionnaire titled "Condition of Service and Staff Job Performance Questionnaire (CSSJPQ)". The questionnaire was structured in a modified four-point Likert rating scale. The validity of the instrument was established by experts in school of education from the department of Educational Administration and Planning. The reliability of the instrument was obtained using Cronbach's Alpha reliability test with a sample of 26 respondents. The reliability coefficient of the instrument is 0.787. The research instrument was administered by the researcher himself, with the help of one assistant in each of the "12" sampled post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. Collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics. In particular, frequency count, simple percentage and mean score were used in answering research questions. The analysis was conducted with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22.

Results

Research Question 1

To what extent does teachers' remuneration, affects their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state?

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Table 1: Impact of Remuneration on Staff Job Performance

Statement	SA (%)	A (%)	DA (%)	SD (%)	M	Decision
Salary paid as at when due, enhances staff management in schools	259 (85%)	46 (15%)	---	---	3.84	Accepted
Regular payment of leave grant, enhances managing staff in schools	225 (74%)	75 (25%)	5 (2%)	---	3.71	Accepted
End of the year bonus encourages staff to work harder and enhances managing them in schools	189 (62%)	70 (23%)	33 (11%)	13 (4%)	3.42	Accepted
Payment of hazard allowance, encourages to take risk in their job and enhances managing the staff in schools	183 (60%)	82 (27%)	32 (10%)	8 (3%)	3.44	Accepted
Uncertainty of getting salary at the month end, make staff management in schools more difficult	221 (73%)	84 (27%)	---	---	3.72	Accepted
Provision of housing allowance to staff, enhances managing them in schools	209 (68%)	85 (28%)	8 (3%)	3 (1%)	3.63	Accepted
Payment of disturbance allowance to staff on transfer, make managing them easier in schools	223 (73%)	75 (25%)	4 (1%)	3 (1%)	3.69	Accepted
Leave grant payment to staff, encourages good attitude to work and improve managing staff in schools	205 (67%)	79 (26%)	15 (5%)	6 (2%)	3.58	Accepted
Payment of marking allowance after examinations, improve managing the staff within that period in schools	228 (75%)	71 (23%)	3 (1%)	3 (1%)	3.71	Accepted
Payment of overtime to staff, will enhances managing them within that period in schools	226 (74%)	71 (23%)	8 (3%)	----	3.71	Accepted

Descriptive statistics was used in examining the impact of remuneration on job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. From the above table, computed responses shows that the respondents were of the view that Salary paid as at when due, (M= 3.84), regular payment of leave grant (M= 3.71), end of year bonus (M= 3.42), payment of hazard allowance M= 3.44), provision of housing allowance (M= 3.72), having certainty in salary payment (M= 3.63), leave grant payment (M= 3.69), payment of disturbance allowance (M= 3.58) marking allowance payment (M= 3.71) payment of overtime (M= 3.71) were all having an impact on staff performance and management in school. Based on the obtained result, it was evident that prompt remuneration to staff has a considerable impact on their performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone.

Research Question 2

To what extent does teachers' promotion affect their job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano State?

Table 2: Impact of Promotion on Staff Performance

Item	SA (%)	A (%)	DA (%)	SD (%)	M	Decision
Regular promotion of staff, ease managing them in schools	241 (79%)	64 (21%)	---	---	3.79	Accepted
Promotion of staff, enhances managing them in schools	225 (74%)	80 (26%)	---	---	3.73	Accepted
Payment of arrears, enhances managing staff in schools	243 (80%)	62 (20%)	---	---	3.79	Accepted
Refusing to promote staff who failed promotional examination, ease managing them in schools	183 (60%)	95 (31%)	14 (5%)	13 (4%)	3.46	Accepted
Verification of credentials before promoting staff encourages genuineness, and ease managing them in schools	219 (72%)	82 (27%)	4 (1%)	---	3.70	Accepted
Oral interview as a criterion for staff promotion, enhances managing them in schools	221 (73%)	84 (27%)	---	---	3.72	Accepted

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Annual Performance Appraisal Form as a criterion for staff promotion, enhances their management in schools	207 (68%)	91 (30%)	7 (2%)	---	3.65	Accepted
Promotion as a basic criterion, enhances management of staff in schools	218 (72%)	87 (28%)	---	---	3.71	Accepted
Writing examination as a criterion for staff promotion, enhances managing them in schools	222 (73%)	83 (27%)	---	---	3.72	Accepted
Increment of salary after promotion, enhances managing staff in schools	226 (74%)	79 (26%)	---	---	3.74	Accepted

Descriptive statistics was also used to examine the impact of promotion on staff performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. From the table, computed responses shows that the respondents were of the view that regular promotion (M= 3.79), promotion of staff (M= 3.73), payment of arrears (M= 3.79), non-payment of staff who failed promotion examination (M= 3.46), verification of credentials (M= 3.70), deployment of oral interview for staff promotion (M= 3.72), annual performance appraisal (M= 3.65), deployment of promotion as basic criterion (M= 3.71), and writing of examination (M= 3.72) were all having a considerable impact on staff performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone.

Research Question 3

To what extent does staff development affect teachers job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano State?

Table 3: Impact of Staff Development on Job Performance

Item	SA (%)	A (%)	DA (%)	SD (%)	M	Decision
In-service training towards staff career development enhances their management in schools	219 (72%)	86 (28%)	---	---	3.71	Accepted
Giving orientation to newly recruited teachers improve their commitment, and enhances their management in schools	216 (71%)	89 (29%)	---	---	3.70	Accepted
Seminar helps staff acquire skills and improve their responsibilities, and enhance their management in schools	211 (69%)	94 (31%)	---	---	3.69	Accepted
Attending conferences stimulate teachers to give in their best, and enhances their management in schools	205 (67%)	98 (32%)	2 (1%)	---	3.66	Accepted
Acquisition of higher qualification by staff, promotes their management in schools	188 (62%)	117 (38%)	---	---	3.61	Accepted
Regular attendance of workshop by staff, enhances their management in schools	172 (56%)	133 (44%)	---	---	3.56	Accepted
Training of teachers on leadership and management, enhances their management in schools	195 (64%)	110 (36%)	---	---	3.63	Accepted
Staff training on area of specialization, help to enhance their management in schools	190 (62%)	115 (38%)	---	---	3.62	Accepted
Induction for new recruited teachers, enhances their management in schools	223 (73%)	82 (27%)	---	---	3.73	Accepted
Re-orientation of teachers in the school, enhances their management in schools	152 (50%)	153 (50%)	---	---	3.49	Accepted

Descriptive statistics was also used in examining the impact of staff development on job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. From the table above, computed responses shows that the respondents were of the view that in-service teacher training (M= 3.71), orientation exercise (M= 3.70), seminars (M= 3.69), conference attendance (M= 3.66), acquisition of higher qualification (M= 3.61), workshop attendance (M= 3.56), leadership skills training (M= 3.63), training of area of specialization (M= 3.62), induction (M= 3.73) and reorientation (M= 3.49) were all having a considerable impact on job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa education zone of Kano state.

Discussion of Findings

This study examined the Impact of Condition of Service on Job Performance in Post Basic Education Schools in Nassarawa Educational zone, Kano State. The objectives of the study are to examine the impact of remuneration, promotion and staff development on job performance in schools. Findings of the study revealed that remuneration package has a significant impact on teachers' job performance in schools. This was based on the computed mean scores which were all above 2.0 level. Such, finding was in line with the work of Udeozor (2004) that remuneration has much influence on staff motivation, job satisfaction, commitment, performance and productivity. Thus, it becomes necessary for all categories of employers of teachers in both the public and private educational institutions to carefully handle all issues concerning staff remuneration with utmost greater rationality if teachers are to improve their job performance.

Similarly, the study revealed that promotion has significant impact on teachers' job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state. This was based on the obtained mean scores which were all above 2.0 levels. The findings were in line with the work of Ige (2014) who postulated that teachers that spent more years than stipulated on a particular grade level without getting promotion usually feel discouraged and became frustrated with the teaching job resulting in poor discharge of responsibilities which negatively affect the set educational goals. Therefore, it is necessary and very clear that teachers' employers particularly at different levels of government should ensure that teachers have their promotion as at when due in order for the teachers to enhance their job performance.

The study equally found that staff development has significant impact on teachers' job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone, Kano state. This was also based on the obtained mean scores which were also above 2.0 levels. The result was in line with the work of Aloma (2012) that staff development prepares workers to improve job understanding, promote job performance and establish future goals for career growth of workers, including teachers. He pointed out that training is necessary for all categories of staff to improve their performance and prepare them for promotion.

Conclusion

Conclusion should be drawn from findings and discussed in prose. Don't itemize it. Based on the findings of the study, remuneration package has a significant impact on teachers' job performance in schools. This was based on the computed mean score which was above 2.0 level. Similarly, the study revealed that promotion has significant impact on teachers' job performance in post basic education schools. This was based on the obtained mean score which was also above 2.0 level. The study equally found that staff development has significant impact on teachers' job performance in post basic education schools in Nassarawa educational zone. This was also based on the obtained mean score which similarly was also above 2.0 level.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations were given:

1. **Special Teachers Salary Scale:** The remuneration package for teachers should be reviewed to much similar higher lucrative packages like the Federal Inland Revenue Service, Nigerian Maritime Administration and Safety Agency, Nigerian Communication Commission, Energy Commission of Nigeria, Nigerian National Petroleum Corporation Customs Service, and Banking of industry etc. This will not only motivate teachers to be at their best but to also attract and retain the best brains in the teaching profession.
2. **Periodic Promotion:** There should be an efficient and periodic promotion that will allow Teachers to be having prompt promotion as at when due. This will motivate teachers like their counterpart workers to enhances their job performance in all level of educational institutions particularly in post basic education schools in Nassarawa Educational zone.
3. **Regular Staff Development Programme:** There is the need to regularly allow the teachers to attend workshops, seminars, conferences and refresher courses in order to become more updated on the contemporary skills concerning teaching and learning activities. Such acquired updated skills, will go a long way to motivate the teachers to improve their job performance.

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